

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATUS OF RISK MANAGEMENT IN THE FINANCIAL SECTOR OF AZERBAIJAN

Yusifov Elshad Masim

Phd, Associate Professor, Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction

ORCID ID: 0000-0003-1946-2937

Hummatov Nijat Mayis

Master student, Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction

ORCID ID: 0009-0005-5515-3658

Abstract

The article analyzes the system of indicators of financial resources management of financial institutions, mainly banks, which are the main participants in financial relations. The dynamic analysis of liquidity and credit risks, as well as trends in change, are discussed in accordance with the indicators presented on the basis of financial statements. Also, the professional integration of modern technologies into the operational process is proposed as a preventive tool.

Keywords: credit risk, liquidity risk, financial relations, management, risk analysis.

Sustainability of economic development in Azerbaijan is one of the main goals of macroeconomic policy. The emergence of this need can be seen in the economies of Azerbaijan and other CIS countries that have transitioned to a market economy, as well as in the management of companies operating in various areas of the private sector, including industry. [1; 2; 7; 9; 10; 11; 12]

Achieving macroeconomic goals depends on various reasons, first of all, on the effective organization of financial management in the country. Naturally, macro goals and activities directly guide the general activity of economic entities at the micro level, as well as the management of financial resources. The economic environment in the country, the regulation of financial relations, interest rates, deposit insurance, exemptions and restrictions applied to money transfers, as well as the fight against illegal financing and money circulation affect the management of financial resources at the macro and micro levels, as well as the risks arising in the management process. In this regard, it is important to note that the situation in the country's financial sector, sustainable development, transparent environment, reliability play an important role in economic growth and macroeconomic stability. Therefore, first of all, the proper organization of financial risk management, the effective activity of financial control and management bodies, the establishment of mutually beneficial relations with economic entities, as well as the implementation of reporting in accordance with international standards, allow for the proper management of risks and the minimization of their possible effects.

It should be noted that issues related to financial risk management in Azerbaijan are relevant from several aspects. This can be characterized by the special sensitivity of the process of managing financial resources to market elements. Risks in financial relations in Azerbaijan can lead to more acute consequences due to the country's integration into the international economic system. Integration has taken place comprehensively. Thus, the deepening of import-

export operations, the fact that the main sources of income are raw material exports, and the constant volatility of the prices of exported basic commodities on the international market lead to the emergence of financial risks that can also manifest themselves in the activities of economic entities in the country. First of all, the effects are reflected in the activities of banks and other financial institutions, as the main participants and driving forces of the financial sector and financial relations. If the banking system demonstrates resilience to financial risks, then the risks do not have a significant impact on the activities of other economic entities. In connection with the above, it should be emphasized that financial risks arise from international or macroeconomic reasons and disrupt the rhythm of the activities of financial and banking sector entities, in what we conditionally call a top-down approach, that is, the direct or indirect impact of problems originating in the banking sector on the management of financial resources of economic entities belonging to other sectors. Bottom-up, on the other hand, is the occurrence of massive financial problems, non-repayment of loan funds, as well as non-fulfillment of other financial obligations in the country's financial sector as a result of economic entities' improper financial management activities. Currently, in order to prevent both situations in time and minimize the impact of the human factor, it is possible to establish early warning systems for possible shortcomings and risk probabilities through the application of artificial intelligence. Therefore, the application of new technologies in financial risk management at both micro and macro levels is an inevitable necessity.

When studying and analyzing risks in the financial sector of Azerbaijan from any context, it is first necessary to determine the impact of banks as an economic entity and as a systemically important element in the country. Because, due to the maximum sensitivity in the management of financial resources, banks apply new standards and modern innovations in important areas such as financial management, risk management, etc. Commercial banks of Azerbaijan are

an important segment of the country's financial market. [3]

In international practice, large banks are mainly engaged in both commercial and investment banking. Commercial banking, among other things, also includes the above-mentioned deposit acceptance and lending activities. Investment banking is engaged in assisting companies in increasing debt and capital, advising on mergers and acquisitions, major corporate restructurings and other corporate financial decisions. Large banks are also often involved in securities trading. [8, p. 25].

The Central Bank of the Republic of Azerbaijan is almost responsible for the efficiency of the country's banking system. In this regard, the decision of the Board of Directors of the Central Bank of the Republic of Azerbaijan on January 28, 2025 is of great importance. The decision on the approval of the "Rules for the Management of Operational Risks in Banks" also includes the rules for the management of operational risks. The rules generally reflect the management system related to operational risks, general policy, methods of identifying and assessing risks, as well as tools, monitoring risks, the organization of their reporting, as well as control, etc. other factors. [5]

The revival of economic activity in the country depends on the level of provision of financial resources to economic entities. Naturally, the issue of providing financial resources does not only include the allocation of funds from state and private sources for the activities of economic entities. Provision also requires the compliance of the allocated funds with the policy of matching the aggregate demand and

supply of money. Proper management and control of funds in the hands of economic entities is also an important factor in risk management. Since the main source of financing is bank loans, serious control measures are also implemented in this area. The decision on approval of the "Rules for managing credit risks in banks", approved by the Central Bank of the Republic of Azerbaijan on September 21, 2023, reflects, in particular, the rules for managing credit risks. [6]

In Azerbaijan, banks and other financial institutions have always played an innovative role in financial risk management, applying international standards and technologies, as well as control and monitoring procedures. Therefore, the risk management measures of banks affect the state of financial stability in the country at the macro and micro levels. Almost all economic entities in the country have entered into financial-credit relations with banks. Therefore, these economic entities also become executors of new technologies, standards and control-inspection procedures based on existing requirements. In financial stability, the influence of banks and economic entities, as well as other persons, on the correct management of risks formed in credit relations in which they are participants is very important. In this regard, the level of credit risk in the country and what measures are implemented to manage it will allow clarifying and analyzing the current situation. Here, banks also apply new technologies and processes. In general, it is necessary to study the official reports of the Central Bank in order to analyze existing credit risks. Figure 1 below reflects the current credit risks of the banking system.

Figure 1. Credit risk in the banking system in Azerbaijan

Source: [4, p. 30]

Figure 1 does not take into account risks on consumer loans. Of course, consumer loans increase economic activity, but since their management depends on the subjective decisions of individuals, they cannot be included in the object of the study. If we look at the level of risks arising on loans allocated to various areas of activity from the perspective of 2024, we can say that the situation here is satisfactory. In 2023, risk indicators also tended to decrease, and the main impact on this decrease can be attributed to the revocation of the licenses of two commercial banks that lost their solvency. In general, as a result of the new management approach and the use of new technologies applied in the banking sector since 2017, risks are being kept under control. One of the main decisions in the management of financial resources was the introduction of a new

monetary framework. This allows banks to maintain liquidity at an acceptable level. The most important indicator here is the level of the liquidity coverage ratio. The Central Bank's "Financial Stability" report for 2024 reflects the real indicators of the corresponding ratio in aggregate, as well as in foreign currency. Thus, as a result of the research, it can be determined that the aggregate ratio was 150 percent, and in foreign currency - 178 percent. The indicators of this ratio ensure the maintenance of the adequacy of high-quality liquid assets, increasing the ability of financial institutions to respond quickly to liquidity problems in the short term.

Figure 2 below reflects the dynamics of the currency structure of liquid assets in the country's banking sector.

Figure 2. Structural dynamics of liquid assets in Azerbaijan, in billion manats

Source: [4, p. 28]

According to the figure, it should be noted that the share of the national currency in the composition of liquid assets, which play an important role in the management of financial resources, is increasing. In

2024 alone, this indicator increased by 4 percentage points compared to 2023, reaching 56 percent. In general, we present the share of foreign currency by year in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. The share of foreign currency in the composition of liquid assets in the country's banking sector

Source: [4, p. 28]

The management of financial risks is affected by the volume of foreign currency use. When analyzing the relevant indicator, it indicates a strengthening of the impact on liquidity in terms of manat. This also allows reducing possible risks through proper management of currency risks. Starting from 2016, a decrease of 23 percentage points occurred by 2024. This estimate is a relative decrease of 34 percent. From an economic point of view, the decrease should be assessed as an increase in the economic impact of the manat, as we have noted. This should be associated with several factors. Thus, there has been an improvement in regulatory activity in the national economy and optimization of the activities of banks. Also, an increase in profitability in manat, as well as an increase in the volume of deposits, has an impact.

Conclusion. The conducted analyses show that proper management in the banking sector as a systemically important element in the management of financial resources in Azerbaijan has been possible mainly through the use of modern technologies. The increase in the use of banking applications, and the encouragement of banks for this, play a serious role in correctly predicting consumer behavior and making general economic decisions more operational, flexible and adequate to the real situation.

In addition, special attention in the banking sector was paid to reducing the amount of required deposits of economic entities, which naturally led to a decrease in

liquidity in total assets. The new approach allowed to strengthen liquid funds. It is possible to apply new approaches, technologies and methods to minimize risks in transactions with financial resources not only on loans issued, but also on financial resources received.

References

1. Abdullayev, K., Abdullayev, R., Yusifov, E., Babazade, I., & Fataliyeva, G. (2024). Main directions of the development of the digital economy in the Republic of Azerbaijan. *Economics of Development*, 23(1), 78-88. <https://doi.org/10.57111/econ/1.2024.78>
2. Abdullayev, K., Yusifov, E., Tazabekova, T., Tkachenko, A., & Mezheryskiy, D. (2025). International trade and its implementation: Studying the impact on the economic development of Azerbaijan, Kyrgyzstan, and Ukraine. *International Journal of Accounting and Economics Studies*, 12(2), 347-360. <https://doi.org/10.14419/9>
3. Bayramov, M. Risk typologies and their mitigation in banking: a of Azerbaijani banks / *Scientific Research International Scientific Journal - 2024* Volume: 4 Issue: 10, pp. 57-60
4. Central Bank of the Republic of Azerbaijan, *Financial stability report*, Baku – 2024, 86 p. <https://uploads.cbar.az/as-sets/98a6608d0eb4e83b612fde01f.pdf>
5. Decision of the Board of Directors of the Central Bank of the Republic of Azerbaijan on

- approval of the “Rules for Managing Operational Risks in Banks” - Baku, January 28, 2025 [Electronic resource] <https://e-qanun.az/framework/58966>
6. Decision of the Board of Directors of the Central Bank of the Republic of Azerbaijan on approval of the “Rules for credit risk management in banks” - Baku, September 21, 2023 [Electronic resource] <https://e-qanun.az/framework/55294>
7. Ismayilov, V., Ibrahimli, C., Yusifov, E., Nasirova, O., Kamran, & Shykyly, K. (2024). An econometric model of the dependence of economic growth of GDP on a group of factors. *Journal of Ecohumanism*, 3(8), 12137-12150. <https://doi.org/10.62754/joe.v3i8.5814>
8. John C. Hull, *Risk Management and Financial Institutions* / Fourth edition, Published by John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey – 2015, p. 743
9. Miniailenko, I., Byba, V., Yusifov, E., & Pavelieva, A. (2022). The role of financial and investment potential in achieving economical equilibrium in construction. *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering*, 181, 677-696. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-85043-2_64
10. Yusifov, E. (2021). Level of implementation and development directions of innovations in the field of construction and investment in Azerbaijan. *Building Innovations*, Poltava, Ukraine, 20-21 June, pp. 323-327.
11. Yusifov, E., Ibrahimov, Kh. (2025). Management of staff in hybrid and remote work models. *Scientific Discussion* (Prague, Czech Republic), 103(1), 51-56.
12. Yusifov, E., Sarkarli, A., & Kushnirova, T. (2022). Analysis of the role and place of the building materials industry in the development of Azerbaijan’s economy. *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering*, 181, 809-819. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-85043-2_74